

Relativity once over easy

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A non-zero matrix $Q(x)$ of the form

$$Q(x) = \begin{pmatrix} a(x) & b(x) \\ b(x) & a(x) \end{pmatrix}$$

is a Minkowski matrix

$$H(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh(x) & \sinh(x) \\ \sinh(x) & \cosh(x) \end{pmatrix}$$

if and only if **[1]**

$$Q(x + y) = Q(x)Q(y)$$

This property looks suspiciously 'exponential'; and indeed, the exponential of the Pauli matrix

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

and the Cayley-Hamilton Theorem confirm this suspicion **[2]**:

$$\exp(x\sigma_1) = Q(x) = H(x)$$

To obtain the relativistic transformation in Einstein form, hyperbolic identities and the Varičák assignment **[3]** $\tanh(x) = v/c$ recast the Minkowski matrix as

$$H(v) = \gamma \begin{pmatrix} 1 & v/c \\ v/c & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

where as usual

$$\gamma = \gamma(v) = (1 - v^2/c^2)^{-1/2}$$

is the Lorentz factor. From here, Sternberg bracketing with the light 'matrix' **[4]**

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} c & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

as

$$\mathbf{SH}(v)\mathbf{S}^{-1}$$

yields the famed transformation.

[1] <https://zenodo.org/records/15624865>

[2] <https://zenodo.org/records/3525985>

[3] V. Varičák: 'Application of Lobachevskian geometry to the theory of relativity', *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, **11** (1910), pp. 93-96.; English translation by Wikisource.

[4] S. Sternberg: *Curvature in Mathematics and Physics* - Dover Publications (2012), Ch. 11.